

Technological Development and Resource Constraints: A Critical Analysis

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Abstract

The world continues to transform with technological advances, but limited resources are a significant obstacle to this progress. This article examines the complex relationship between technological progress and resource limitations. Mathematical models show how various factors influence technology adoption rates, including knowledge, skills, access, government policy, and the availability of new technology. Limited resources such as capital, labor, and raw materials can hinder technological progress by increasing costs, slowing innovation, and limiting implementation. The discussion in this article provides several suggestions for further research in terms of research and development, policy and strategy, such as formulating policies that encourage responsible and sustainable technology adoption, as well as ensuring fair access to new technology and improving education in the fields of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics, and provide comprehensive and accessible technology training programs.

Keywords: Technological Development, Technology Adoption, Resource Constraints, Sustainable Technology

1. Introduction

Technology keeps developing and is crucial to a country's economic growth. Previous studies have discussed various aspects, including innovation and adoption of technology, where emphasizing the importance of progress technology To spur growth and economic sustainability, especially in developing countries (Das et al., 2020; Seo et al., 2020). However, limitations in source Power are a necessary barrier considered (Das et al., 2020; Núñez-López et al., 2014). Another study looked at innovation technology from corner look companies, especially in industry telecommunications, and showed a positive connection between innovation and excellent competition (Wanaswa et al., 2021). However, small and medium enterprises in developing countries face challenges in adopting new technology, like limitations in source Power finances and knowledge (Zhao et al., 2022).

Other articles also discuss the importance of environment-supporting technology for sustainability for SMEs (Zhao et al., 2022). Draft This aligned with findings that source internal power, such as the ability to absorb new technology, is more significant in SME sustainability than source Power external, like access to the global market (Kozłowski & Matejun, 2011). The following article uses approach modeling to study dynamics change technology (Xue & Xu, 2017). This model considers the limitations of source power and its efficiency in adopting technology. Thus, the seventh article comprehensively describes various factors affecting innovation and technology adoption. Discussions were carried out. This will more specifically discuss how limitations of power influence dynamics change technology, focusing on mechanisms of coexistence and mutual technology competition. This article discusses a few

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models that combine adoption technology with allocation source Power limited finances. Through analysis of variant internal and external innovation and framework work dynamics, the article aims to explain how related technology can survive and live side by side tightly.

2. Theoretical basis

Technological change is a dynamic process that involves the creation, adoption, and diffusion of new technologies. Scientific progress, economic needs, and social change drive this process. However, limited resources such as capital, labor, and raw materials can hinder this process. Schumpeterian theory explains that innovative entrepreneurs ("Schumpeterian entrepreneurs") need resources to develop and commercialize new technologies (Núñez-López et al., 2014).

Neo-Schumpeterian theory extends Schumpeterian theory by considering the role of institutions and networks in technological change. Effective innovation systems can help overcome resource constraints and encourage faster innovation (Das et al., 2020). The theory of technological evolution suggests that technology develops through natural selection, where the technology best suited to its environment survives and develops. Resource limitations can influence the types of technology designed and adopted (Wanaswa et al., 2021). The ecological theory of technology shows the importance of considering technological change's social and environmental impacts when formulating technology policy. Limited natural resources and the ecological impact of new technologies can encourage the development of more sustainable technologies (Xue & Xu, 2017).

Inspired by biological evolution, evolutionary economics views markets and technologies as evolving systems that adapt to changing environments. New ideas, products, and processes emerge through variation, selection, and retention, similar to how new species develop in nature (Das et al., 2020). This theory helps us understand the long-term evolution of industries and markets. Still, it can struggle to predict specific outcomes due to these processes' complex and dynamic nature.

Institutional theory focuses on how rules, norms, and social structures (institutions) shape economic behavior and outcomes. Institutions can constrain and enable individual and organizational actions, influencing innovation and financial activities (Zhao et al., 2022). This theory helps us understand how institutions like property rights impact innovation. Still, critics argue it can overemphasize institutions and neglect the role of individual agencies and market forces in shaping economic outcomes.

Complexity theory provides a framework for understanding complex systems like innovation and technological change. These systems involve many interacting components, nonlinear relationships, and emergent properties – new behaviors arising from the system, not its individual parts. This theory helps us understand the dynamics of innovation by emphasizing interconnectedness and adaptation (Wanaswa et al., 2021; Xue & Xu, 2017). Still, it can be challenging to formalize mathematically and test empirically due to these systems' complex and dynamic nature.

Discussion of the seventh article can be seen in the following summary of Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison Seven Research Articles Previously

Title	Theoretical framework	Findings Study
A Study on the Mechanisms Linking Environmental Dynamism to Innovation Performance	Diversification Theory Technology	Technology-enabled SMEs can compete in the global market.
		Promotional policies digitalization can increase activity in the economy
Dynamic Influence of Digital and Technological Advancement on Sustainable Economic Growth in Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) Countries	Excellence Theory Competitive Porter	Innovation technology has its influence on excellence and competitive
		Cultural innovation and management strategy source adequate power necessary for a successful company.
Technology Adaptation and Survival of SMEs: A Longitudinal Study of Developing Countries	Institutional Theory	Environment-supporting technology is essential For SME sustainability
	Ecosystem Theory Innovation	The ability to access internal institutions (e.g., availability of technology, absorption, and infrastructure) is more important than the ability to access external (e.g., access to foreign markets).
Influence Factor Analysis of Enterprise IT Innovation Capacity Based on System Dynamics	Economic Growth Theory	E-government development has an impact on the sustainable growth of the economy.
	Electronic Governance Theory	Policies that promote e-government can increase efficiency and transparency in the public sector.
The Dynamics of Technological Change Under Constraints: Adopters and Resources	Modeling Theory Mathematics	Limitations source Power can influence dynamics change technology
	Dynamics Adaptive	Internal and external innovation play an essential role in the evolution of technology.
Mechanism coexistence is possibly related to technology tightly. For life, it is side by side.		
Dynamic Business Environment as a Source of Technology Entrepreneurship Development: A Case Study of MakoLab SA	Development entrepreneurship technology	Environment-dynamic and complex businesses offer opportunities For entrepreneurship technology. MakoLab SA uses various strategies to navigate the environment's dynamic business.
	Schumpeter and Drucker's theory of entrepreneurship	MakoLab SA uses various strategies to navigate the environment's dynamic business.

Title	Theoretical framework	Findings Study
Technological Innovation and Competitive Advantage: Empirical Evidence from Large Telecommunication Firms	Superiority competitive	Innovation technology's connection is moderately positive with superiority competitive.
	Network technology theory innovation by Rogers (1983)	Innovation technology explained 12.2% of the variation in superiority competitive

Understanding the relationship between technological change and resource constraints is critical to formulating effective policies that encouraging innovation and economic growth while considering new technologies' social and environmental impacts (Das et al., 2020).

3. Discussion

Technological advances continue to transform the world. Discoveries and innovations continue to emerge, revolutionizing how humans live and work. However, behind this progress, there is an essential factor that is often overlooked: resource limitations. This article examines the complex relationship between technological development and resource constraints.

- **Adoption Technology: Internal and External Dynamics**

The user technology adoption model explains how the level of technology adoption is influenced by two main factors, namely internal and external factors. Internal factors include knowledge, skills, access, attitudes and user needs towards technology. Meanwhile, external factors include social influences, social media, government policies, the economy and new technology. These two factors are interrelated and interact to influence the level of technology adoption. A better understanding of these factors can assist individuals, organizations, and policymakers promote effective and beneficial technology adoption. This model shows that good internal and external factors play a role in determining how fast and extensive technology is adopted. Accessible technology studied and used, with adequate infrastructure and support from a strong community, tends to be adopted quickly. On the other hand, complex and expensive technology, with limited support and a lack of public infrastructure awareness, may experience adoption obstacles.

- **Limitations Resource: Obstacle in Progress**

Limited resources such as capital, labor and raw materials can hinder technological progress. The costs of developing and implementing new technology are increasing, making the technology less affordable. This impacts small businesses, individuals, and developing countries. A lack of resources also slows down research and development, thereby hindering the creation of new technologies and affecting the overall rate of technological progress. Additionally, resource constraints can limit the ability to adopt new technologies, even if desired. This creates a technology gap where some parties have access while others are left behind. Effective policies and strategies must consider these factors to ensure all parties can access and utilize new technologies.

- **Equilibrium and Coexistence: Complex Market Dynamics**

This model describes the equilibrium points at which the level of technology adoption stabilizes. This balance can be full adoption by all users, incomplete adoption by only some users, or the coexistence of several competing technologies in the market. Factors such as the availability of new technology, a company's ability to absorb the technology, and

internet usage influence whether the technology achieves full adoption, incomplete adoption, or coexistence. Understanding these market dynamics is essential for formulating effective business strategies and technology policies.

- **Impact Important: Efficiency Smart Adoption Resources and Strategies**

Findings from previous studies show that efficient source power and innovative adoption strategies have become vital to successful technology. Economic technology source power and its strategic adoption tend to reach widespread adoption and survive in the market.

Efficiency source power, like using minimal materials and low energy consumption, overcomes limitations in source power and makes technology more affordable. This makes it attractive for users with limited budgets or who care about the environment. Apart from efficiency source power, an intelligent adoption strategy is also essential. This can cover campaign marketing targeted, training programs comprehensive user, and assignment models price affordable. By combining both, companies increase opportunity technology For success.

4. Conclusions and recommendations

Progress technology is like a double-edged knife. On one side, technology revolutionizes methods of living, working and interacting with the world, opening up opportunities For progress in the economy, society and culture. On the other hand, progress is not free from limitations and source power, which becomes a challenge in the optimal adoption and utilization of technology. This article has discussed the complex connection between development technology and constraints source Power. The mathematical model shows How various internal and external factors, such as knowledge, skills, access to technology, the influence of social media, policy government, and availability of new technology, influence the level of adoption of technology. This model also shows How limitations in source Power, such as capital, energy work, and raw materials, can hinder the progress of technology with increased cost, slow innovation, and limited implementation. Understanding connection is vital For formulating effective and ensuring policies benefit technology all parties enjoy.

Following are some suggestions for further study furthermore :

- **Research and Development:** Encourage research and development of technology economical source power, using minimal ingredients, low energy consumption, and cycle repeat. Support research and development technology, such as new ones that help overcome limitations of source power, like renewable energy, technology, agriculture sustainability, and management of waste efficiently. Push collaboration between public and private sectors to maximize source power and speed up the progress of technology.
- **Policy and Strategy:** Formulate encouraging policies for adopting responsible and sustainable technology. Ensure all parties, including communities in remote and developing countries, have access to new technology. Upgrade digital literacy and public awareness about the benefits and risks of technology to promote responsible adoption.
- **Education and Training:** Improve education in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics. I want to produce power and work skills and be ready to face challenges in future technology. Hold a training program that is comprehensive and easy to access to increase the capacity of individuals and organizations to adopt and utilize new technology effectively. Focus education and training on the development of adaptive skills, like thinking critically, solving problems, and communication, which makes it possible for individuals to Keep going, learn and adapt to change fast technology.

- Collaboration and Partnership: Build cooperation between public, private, and academic sectors to overcome challenges in developing and adopting sustainable technology. Create a global partnership to share knowledge, technology, and resources to ensure everyone enjoys technology worldwide. Get involved public civil in the retrieval process of related technology To ensure technology is developed and used responsibly, responsibly, and ethically.

Understanding related challenges and opportunities with development technology and constraints source power can help us build a better, sustainable future where technology can be utilized optimally to increase the quality of life for humans. We need a collective effort from the government, the private sector, academics and society for work. The same is true in building a better future where technology can push progress and prosperity for all.

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